

BitNN: A Bit-Serial Accelerator for K-Nearest Neighbor Search in Point Clouds

This version provides detailed formula derivation in the APPENDIX

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Abstract—Point cloud-based machine perception applications have achieved great success in various scenarios. In this work, we focus on point cloud k-Nearest Neighbor (kNN) search, an important kernel for point clouds. Existing kNN acceleration techniques have overlooked the operation-level optimization in the Euclidean distance computation operations, which suffer from low efficiency due to a number of unnecessary computations and various data precision requirements.

We reconsider point cloud kNN search from a new bit-serial computation perspective and propose BitNN, a bit-serial architecture for point cloud kNN search. BitNN supports adaptive precision processing and unnecessary computing reduction, significantly improving the performance and power efficiency of kNN search. To achieve that, we first propose a bit-serial computation method for kNN search, which derives a recursive expression to compute the Euclidean distance bit by bit. Then, the dimension-wise point cloud encoding method and point-wise data layout method are proposed to enable adaptive precision processing based on bit-serial computation. Furthermore, we present an early termination mechanism for bit-serial kNN search. By estimating the lower bound of distance based on a few bits, a number of unnecessary computations can be reduced. Finally, we design an efficient bit-serial accelerator for kNN search. The accelerator exploits the massive parallelism to improve computing efficiency.

We evaluate BitNN with several widely used point cloud datasets. BitNN achieves up to $6.6\times$ speedup and $3.6\times$ power efficiency compared to a comparable sized architecture. Moreover, BitNN can be easily integrated into existing bit-parallel kNN accelerators. We enhance the state-of-the-art kNN accelerator,

ParallelNN, with bit-serial computation techniques, achieving up to $4.4\times$ speedup and $2.9\times$ power efficiency.

Index Terms—k-nearest neighbor search, bit-serial, accelerators, point clouds

I. INTRODUCTION

A point cloud is a collection of points that directly represents a physical object or 3D scene. Recently, with the emerging interest in 3D geometry-based algorithms, point clouds have been extensively employed across diverse scenarios such as autonomous driving, robotics and virtual reality/augmented reality (VR/AR). The k-Nearest Neighbor (kNN) search is a key primitive operation for the 3D point cloud, which aims to find the k nearest neighbors for a given query point. The kNN search often lies in the critical path of point cloud-based applications, such as machine perception [46] [8], 3D reconstruction [7], simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) [33] [30] [51], etc. Many benchmarks show that the kNN search can take up to 80% of total runtime [16] [36] [48]. These applications often operate within energy-constrained environments, posing significant challenges for real-time and energy-efficient processing.

Currently, several domain-specific kNN accelerators have been presented to tackle this challenge. Among them, partition-based kNN search accelerators, such as QuickNN [36] and ParallelNN [9], are the most efficient kNN search acceleration architecture. They achieve a trade-off between

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time efficiency and search accuracy. First, the point cloud is broken into multiple small regions. Then, for a given query point, it selectively searches for neighboring points within a specific region, significantly reducing the search space. Several optimization techniques are also proposed to tackle irregular memory access. Although existing accelerators have extensively explored the algorithm and architecture-level optimization of kNN search, there is still a performance gap in meeting the real-time processing requirements when the point cloud scale becomes large. We have conducted a case study and found that the Euclidean distance computation, the most basic operation for point cloud kNN search, accounts for more than 80% of runtime in the state-of-the-art implementation [9].

When executing the kNN search, existing accelerators first completely load the coordinate data of two points and then calculate the Euclidean distance between two points. However, we observe that accurate distance calculation is unnecessary for all points. For instance, consider a 1NN task, which aims to find the nearest point to q (located at $[0, 0, 0]$) among 100 reference points. After traversing 50 reference points, it is assumed that the distance of the current nearest point is 3.14. When traversing to the next point located at $[10.1, 20.4, 30.6]$, we observe that the distance calculation is actually unnecessary because the distance cannot be smaller than 3.14 by a rough estimation. However, existing accelerators have to load the operands and execute at least 8 arithmetic operations for an accurate distance calculation. This results in high memory access and computation costs. In this paper, by using a bit-serial method to estimate the Euclidean distance with only a fraction of bits of the points' coordinates, we can reduce up to 90% of the computation cost and up to 84% of the memory access, significantly improving the performance and energy efficiency of kNN search.

Meanwhile, point cloud data type is another important attribute of kNN distance calculation. Through an extensive exploration of real-world point clouds, we found that the numerical precision required by point clouds varies across scenarios. For instance, a typical LiDAR for autonomous driving [17] has a range of 120 m with 0.01 m accuracy, while a 3D scanner for 3D modeling [1] has a range of 0.2 m with 10^{-6} m accuracy. However, existing implementations rely on a *one-size-fits-all* approach, using the *worst-case* data type for all scenarios, leaving substantial room for performance improvement.

Rather than employing fixed precision for point cloud processing and performing the complete Euclidean distance computation for all points, we explore the Bit-Serial Computation (BSC) technique to achieve higher performance and energy efficiency by supporting both adaptive precision processing and unnecessary computation reduction. Generally, BSC slices multi-bit data into multiple 1-bit data and processes one bit per cycle. Currently, BSC has demonstrated significant success in accelerating deep neural networks (DNNs) [3] [11] [23] [49]. However, bit-serial techniques can not be directly applied in accelerating the kNN search because the kNN search utilizes Euclidean distance to identify neighboring points. The Eu-

clidean distance computation is different from the operations within DNNs. The theory and architecture for the bit-serial computation of Euclidean distance have not been explored.

In this work, we present BitNN, a bit-serial accelerator for k-nearest neighbor search in point clouds, offering a new dimension to improve kNN execution performance. Specifically, we propose a series of innovative mechanisms and architectures, including bit-serial computation, data layout, early termination and parallel architecture. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work that extends the bit-serial computation on kNN for 3D point clouds. The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows.

1) We propose a novel bit-serial computation method for kNN search, which derives a recursive expression to compute the Euclidean distance bit by bit. This method provides a theoretical foundation for the kNN accelerator design.

2) We propose a dimension-wise point cloud encoding method and a point-wise data layout method. These methods can compress the point cloud, further reducing 40.2% off-chip memory access.

3) We present an early termination mechanism for bit-serial kNN search. By estimating the lower bound of the Euclidean distance based on a few bits, a number of unnecessary computations can be reduced. Experiments show this method can even achieve up to 90% computation reduction in some cases.

4) We present an efficient parallel architecture for bit-serial kNN search. The accelerator integrates an array of Bit-serial Distance Units (BDUs). The BDU eliminates the need for multipliers to compute the square distance. The accelerator can achieve up to $6.4\times$ speedup and $3.6\times$ power efficiency compared to the baseline architecture.

It is worth noting that this work focuses on operation-level optimization, which is orthogonal to existing techniques that exploit algorithm and architecture-level optimization. Taking the state-of-the-art ParallelNN accelerator as an example, we replace the architecture that performs distance computation and topK operation with a BDU array and a topK array. The bit-serial based ParallelNN achieves up to $4.4\times$ speedup and $2.9\times$ power efficiency compared to the original ParallelNN.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

A. Point Cloud

A point cloud is a collection of points $P = \{p_i\}$, where each point is represented by $\langle x, y, z \rangle$ in the Cartesian coordinates system. Point clouds are continuously generated by 3D scanners such as LiDARs and depth cameras to perceive the environment. As the sensors become cheaper and miniaturized, point cloud has been employed extensively in many scenarios, such as autonomous driving, robots, etc. Point cloud scale (number of points) and generation frequency (number of frames per second) are two of the most important attributes of 3D scanners. With the development of LiDAR, point clouds are generated with a higher frequency and larger scale, which pose a much higher computation requirement for point cloud applications. The latest LiDAR for autonomous driving generates up to 460,000 points every 50ms [37].

Fig. 1. Illustration of the kNN search and the pipeline execution of Euclidean distance computation and topK operations.

B. kNN Search Algorithms and Accelerators

Point cloud k -nearest neighbor (kNN) search is a case of kNN search in 3D metric space. For a given query point, it finds k nearest neighbor points among a set of reference points. Figure 1(a) illustrates the kNN search for three query points (Q_0, Q_1, Q_2) among eight reference points ($R_0 - R_7$), where $k=3$. Consequently, R_0, R_1 and R_3 are identified as the neighbor points for Q_0 . Generally, the kNN search involves two key operations. As depicted in Figure 1(b), one is the **Euclidean distance computing** operation, which calculates the Euclidean distance between the query point and reference point, and another is the **topK** operation, which selects k reference points with minimized distance. Specially, instead of performing *topK* until all distance computation is complete, which requires a large memory footprint to store the distance results, a common optimization [9] [36] [52] is constructing a temporary list of k nearest points and updating it when every reference point is processed. Therefore, the distance of current k -th nearest neighbor point is available during the kNN search.

kNN search is a crucial operation performed by point cloud applications. For instance, in the odometry estimation tasks within autonomous driving scenarios [38], the algorithm continuously receives multiple frames of point clouds per second from the LiDAR. It utilizes kNN search to establish point correspondences between consecutive frames, facilitating vehicle motion estimation. To fulfill real-time processing requirements, systems must handle millions of points per second. This heavy workload renders kNN one of the most time- and energy-intensive kernels in autonomous vehicle operations [5].

Currently, several domain-specific kNN accelerators have been presented. Among them, partition-based kNN search accelerators, such as QuickNN [36] and ParallelNN [9], are the most efficient kNN search acceleration architecture. These accelerators execute the kNN search in two stages: the partition stage and the search stage. In the partition stage, the kd-tree or octree is employed to partition the large point cloud into multiple small regions. And then, the accelerator assigns each query point to a specific region based on its geometric attribute. In the search stage, the accelerator utilizes multiple computing units to simultaneously perform the Euclidean distance computation and *topK* operations, finding k nearest neighbor points only within a specific region for a given query point, resulting in approximate results.

C. Performance Characterizations

We characterize the kNN search to understand the bottlenecks and identify optimization opportunities. To that end, we profile the performance on various platforms with several scales of point clouds, including CPU, GPU and domain-special point cloud kNN accelerators.

Latency Breakdown. Figure 2 illustrates the latency breakdown of kNN search in three typical applications [51] [53] [46]. The kNN search accounts for approximately 60% to 80% of the total runtime of these applications. Given that these applications are commonly deployed in energy-constrained systems and necessitate real-time interaction with environments, the imperative for low latency and energy-efficient processing of kNN has emerged as a key challenge.

Runtime Analysis. The current implementations cannot meet the real-time processing requirements due to the growing size of point clouds. Figure 3 depicts the runtime of kNN search across various platforms and point cloud scales. The implementations for CPU and GPU are derived from the widely-used FLANN library [32]. A horizontal dashed line denotes the point cloud generation interval of the latest LiDAR [37], serving as a reference for meeting real-time processing requirements. A red point represents the point cloud size. A $2.8\times$ performance gap remains for the state-of-the-art accelerator, highlighting the need to accelerate the kNN search.

Bottleneck Analysis of Partition-based kNN Accelerators. Figure 4 quantifies the runtime breakdown of three partition-based kNN accelerators and non-streaming DRAM access rate. The current partition-based kNN accelerators suffer from high compute costs for two reasons: (i) Partition-based kNN operations entail numerous GOPs. For instance, in the popular LiDAR-based odometry benchmark [17], running a kNN search requires approximately 120 GOPs on a typical constructed scene with about a million-scale point cloud. The computation accounts for more than 80% of the runtime in ParallelNN. The computational overhead mainly comes from the Euclidean distance computing operations. (ii) Previous works [36] [9] [15] [27] [52] efficiently tackle the issue of irregular memory access. SimpleKD [36] is a baseline architecture for partition-based kNN search. It performs standard kd-tree based kNN search, where irregular tree traversal results in inefficiently non-continuous memory accesses. The memory access dominates the runtime. Previous works propose several optimization techniques to address this issue, such as read- and write-gather cache [36], and two-stage tree traveling [15], etc. The state-of-the-art kNN accelerator, ParallelNN [9], further enhances performance by fully adapting kNN search on HBM to leverage the high external bandwidth. Consequently, the redundant DRAM access for reference points is eliminated, and all DRAM accesses become streaming. However, the computation, especially the Euclidean distance computing operation, becomes the performance bottleneck.

The Need for Further Computation Optimization. Existing kNN accelerators cannot meet the real-time processing requirements when the point cloud size exceeds 200K. The

Fig. 2. Latency breakdown of three kNN-based applications [51] [53] [46].

Fig. 3. Runtime of the kNN search on various platforms with several scales of point clouds.

Fig. 4. Runtime breakdown and percentage of non-continuous DRAM access of the kNN search on partition-based kNN accelerators [36] [9].

Fig. 5. Relationship between this work with prior neighbor search accelerators [36] [9] [15] [27] [52].

computational operations dominate the runtime, especially Euclidean distance computing and topK operation. However, performance gains from increasing the number of compute units are diminishing, necessitating a significant investment in additional compute units, which leads to high area overhead and reduced power efficiency [36]. Unlike previous approaches that primarily focus on optimizing irregular memory access, our approach targets kNN operation-level optimization, as depicted in Figure 5. The accelerator achieves higher performance and power efficiency by minimizing unnecessary computing and memory access at the bit level. Importantly, these techniques are orthogonal with existing algorithm-architecture co-design efforts. Combining bit-serial computing techniques with existing accelerators will further enhance performance.

D. Observation and Key idea

Through an extensive exploration of existing implementations, we have three crucial observations that demonstrate the substantial space for kNN search performance improvement, which is shown in Figure 6.

Observation I: Most computations in the Euclidean distance are unnecessary. Figure 6(a) presents an example of a kNN task (1D space is assumed for simplification), which aims to find k nearest points to the query point q located at 153. In the current iteration, the reference point r located at 22 is determined whether it can be added to the nearest neighbor list. In the conventional approach, the complete square Euclidean distance calculation between r and q should be performed. Figure 6(a) shows that the square Euclidean distance is 17161, which is much higher than the current square distance of the k -th nearest neighbor (16 in the example). However, we observe that the result can be deduced by only knowing the most significant 2 bits. In other words, given that the most significant 2 bits of q and r are '10' and '00', it can be ensured that $q \geq 128$ and $r \leq 63$, implying that the square Euclidean distance is definitely greater than 16. The remaining 6 bits will not impact the final result, and the computations involved in these bits are actually unnecessary.

Key idea: We propose a bit-serial Euclidean distance computation mechanism and an early terminated mechanism. The Euclidean distance is computed in a bit-per-bit manner, from

Fig. 6. Three observations of point cloud kNN search.

MSB to LSB of coordinates. The lower bound of the distance is estimated based on a small fraction of bits. In this way, the computation could be terminated as soon as the estimated lower bound exceeds the current k -th distance.

Observation II: The data in point clouds exhibits various ranges and precision. Fixed data type is less efficient for point clouds. The precision requirements of numerical representation for point clouds vary across scenarios and even across dimensions. As shown in Figure 6(b), although LiDARs and 3D scanners are commonly used 3D sensors, their perception range and accuracy are quite different. The LiDAR for geodetic surveying [29] has a range of 2000m with centimeter accuracy, while the 3D scanner for object 3D modeling [1] has a range of 0.2m with micrometer accuracy. Moreover, the range among the three dimensions differs even in a single scenario. We have conducted the distribution of the point cloud coordinates in Waymo dataset [44], which is a typical dataset for autonomous driving. As shown in the middle of Figure 6(b), the results indicate that the range of X and Y dimensions ($-75m \sim 75m$) is much higher than the range of Z dimension ($0m \sim 5m$). However, existing

implementations rely on a *one-size-fits-all* approach, using the *worst-case* data type for all scenarios and all dimensions. For example, most CPU and GPU implementations use floating point data type [26] [13] [12], while recent accelerators use fixed-point data type [9] [27].

Key idea: Based on the bit-serial computation, we propose a dimension-wise point cloud encoding method. The numerical precision for each dimension can be adaptive based on its range and precision.

Observation III: Bits padding causes a waste of external memory accesses. Existing implementations package the point cloud as an array of points. Three fixed-point values or floating-point values represent each point. Furthermore, existing implementations often pad the point data structure to 64 bits [27] [36] [9] to align to the address boundaries. For instance, the ParallelNN accelerator formats a point to 64 bits. As shown in Figure 6(c), three 15-bit fixed-point values store the point’s coordinate, while the remaining 19 bits are used in the kNN search¹. In this way, the effective external memory access is less than 75%. Additionally, the bits padding leads to ineffective on-chip memory utilization, resulting in redundant DRAM access when handling large point cloud data sizes [15].

Key idea: We propose a point-wise data layout method to address this issue. Instead of storing a single point within 64 bits, the point-wise method stores the 1-bit data of 64 points within a 64-bit space. This mapping method can be well combined with the bit-serial computation because the computation is performed one bit per point per cycle.

E. Design Consideration

Bit-Serial Computation (BSC) slices multi-bit data into multiple 1-bit data and processes one bit per cycle. In conjunction with DNN quantization techniques [18], BSC has demonstrated success in accelerating DNNs. By quantize the DNN model into techniques, the operands are the Several works [49] [3] [11] concentrate on inner-product operation, which is the key operation in DNNs. The accelerator can mitigate unnecessary computations by leveraging bit-level sparsity and variable precision of DNN workloads, further improving performance and energy efficiency. However, the Euclidean distance computation is quite different from the operations within DNNs. The computation of Euclidean distance involves additional subtraction operations compared to inner-product operations, and the computational order differs from that of inner-product operations. Existing BSC techniques can not be directly applied in accelerating kNN search. The theory and architecture for bit-serial kNN search have not been explored.

This paper reconsiders the point cloud data type and kNN computing operations from a new bit-serial computation perspective, offering a new dimension to improve kNN execution performance. Specifically, we propose a series of innovative mechanisms and architectures, including bit-serial computation, data layout, early termination and parallel architecture.

¹8 bits for the intensity field, and 11 bits are reserved. The intensity is not used in the Euclidean distance computation.

TABLE I
NOTATIONS.

Notation	Meaning
Q, R	The set of query points and reference points
q, r	The query point and reference point, $q \in Q, r \in R$
B	The bit width of the point coordinate value
q_d	The coordinate value in the d -th dimension of q
$q_{d,b}$	The b -th bit of coordinate value in the d -th dimension of q
$f_{d,b}(q, r)$	The partial subtraction of the coordinate in the d -th dimension between q and r . The q and r only keep most significant b bits
$dist_b^2(q, r)$	The partial square Euclidean distance between q and r . The q and r ’s coordinate only keep most significant b bits
$g_b^2(q, r)$	The estimated lower bound of the square Euclidean distance between q and r with most significant b bits

These new methods and architecture enable the accelerator to support both adaptive precision processing and unnecessary computing reduction, significantly reducing the computation cost and memory accesses. These techniques is orthogonal to existing techniques that explore the algorithm and architecture-level optimization. Combining the bit-serial technique with the existing accelerator will further improve the performance.

III. BIT-SERIAL KNN SEARCH COMPUTATION

In this section, the bit-serial computation of the Euclidean distance (Sec. III-A) is presented. Then, the dimension-wise point cloud encoding method (Sec. III-B) and point-wise data layout method (Sec. III-C) are proposed to compress the point cloud. Subsequently, an early termination mechanism is devised that effectively reduces unnecessary computation (Sec. III-D). Finally, the bit-serial kNN search algorithm is proposed (Sec. III-E). Table I lists the notations used in this section.

A. Bit-Serial Computation of Euclidean Distance

In Cartesian coordinates, the Euclidean distance between two points q and r can be expressed as $\sqrt{\sum_{d=1}^3 (q_d - r_d)^2}$. To avoid performing the square root operation, a common optimization is to calculate the square Euclidean distance.

$$Dist^2(q, r) = \sum_{d=1}^3 (q_d - r_d)^2 \quad (1)$$

By introducing some metrics and a serial of derivations, the Equation (1) is converted into Equation (3), which reveals that the Euclidean distance can be calculated bit by bit from MSB to LSB of point’s coordinates. Then, a recursive expression is given in Equation (4), demonstrating the operations within the bit-serial computation. The key steps are described as follows.

We define two metrics called $dist_m^2(q, r)$ and $f_{d,m}(q, r)$. The $dist_m^2(q, r)$ represents the partial square distance between point q and r when only the most significant m bits of both points’ coordinates are kept. With this definition, the final $Dist^2(q, r)$ equals $dist_B^2(q, r)$, where B is the bit width of the point coordinate. Similarly, the $f_{d,m}(q, r)$ represents the partial subtraction of the coordinates in the d -th dimension

between q and r with only the most significant m bits of both points' coordinates are kept.

$$\begin{aligned} dist_m^2(q, r) &= \sum_{d=1}^3 \left[\sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times 2^{b+m-B} \right]^2 \\ f_{d,m}(q, r) &= \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} [(q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times 2^{b+m-B}] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

After formula derivation, the $dist_m^2(q, r)$ in Equation (2) can be rewritten as Equation (3). The details of derivation are given in Appendix B Theorem 1.

$$\begin{aligned} dist_m^2(q, r) &= 2^{2(m-B)} \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} 2^{2b} \left[\sum_{d=1}^3 [(q_{d,b} - r_{d,b})^2 + \right. \\ &\quad \left. 4 \times (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times f_{d,B-b-1}(q, r)] \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

As we can see, the $\sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} 2^{2b}$ is located at the outer layer of Equation (3), meaning that the square Euclidean distance can be computed in a bit-by-bit style. Specifically, $dist_m^2(q, r)$ equals the sum of m items. When computing the $dist_m^2(q, r)$ from $b = B - 1$ to $b = B - m$, each item only relates to the values of most significant b bits (denoted as $q_{d,b}$, $r_{d,b}$ in Equation (3) and partial subtraction values (denoted as $f_{d,B-b-1}(q, r)$ in Equation (3)). We further transform the Equation (3) into a recursive expression to give a clear view. The details of the transformation are given in Appendix B Corollary 1.

$$\begin{aligned} dist_m^2(q, r) &= \underbrace{dist_{m-1}^2(q, r) \ll 2}_{\text{left shift}} + \sum_{d=1}^3 \underbrace{(q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m})^2}_{\text{square}} + \\ &\quad \sum_{d=1}^3 \underbrace{((q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m}) \times f_{d,m-1}(q, r)) \ll 2}_{\text{left shift}} \\ f_{d,m}(q, r) &= f_{d,m-1}(q, r) \ll 1 + (q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m}) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

As we can see, the $dist_m^2(q, r)$ can be calculated bit by bit in a recursive manner. Specifically, $dist_m^2(q, r)$ is the sum of three components: (1) the left shift of the $dist_{m-1}^2(q, r)$, (2) the sum of the square of the subtraction of most significant m -th bit of q and r for three dimensions, (3) the sum of the left shift on $(q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m}) \times f_{d,m-1}(q, r)$ for three dimensions. Because the result of $q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m}$ can only be -1, 0 or 1, the multiplication operation can be performed by a multiplexer.

As a result, the square Euclidean distance can be computed bit by bit with the adder trees, logical gates and multiplexers. A simplified example is shown in Figure 7. The bit-serial computation performs from MSB to LSB, taking 5 cycles to compute the final result 81. The result is the same as that obtained by normal computation: $(18 - 9)^2 = 81$, corroborating the bit-serial Euclidean distance computation mechanism. The rigorous proof is in Appendix A and B.

		MSB					LSB															
q:		1	0	0	1	0	= 18					r:	0	1	0	0	1	= 9				
Items	m	0	1	2	3	4	5															
$q_{1,B-m}$	-	1	0	0	1	0																
$r_{1,B-m}$	-	0	1	0	0	1																
$q_{1,B-m} - r_{1,B-m}$	-	1	-1	0	1	-1																
$f_{1,m}(q, r)$	0	1	1	2	5	9																
$dist_{m-1}^2(q, r) \ll 2$	-	0	4	4	16	100																
$(q_{0,B-m} - r_{0,B-m})^2$	-	1	1	0	1	1																
$(q_{1,B-m} - r_{1,B-m}) \times f_{d,m-1}(q, r) \ll 2$	-	0	-4	0	8	-20																
$dist_m^2(q, r)$	0	1	1	4	25	81																

Fig. 7. Example of the bit-serial computation of Euclidean distance for two 1-D point q and r . The q is 18 and r is 9.

B. Dimension-Wise Point Cloud Encoding

We present a dimension-wise point cloud encoding method, which can adapt to variable precision requirements. The point cloud encoding consists of three steps.

Scaling and rounding. Point cloud's floating-point coordinates are scaled up and converted into integers. As explained in Section II-D, the accuracy of 3D sensors is limited. Therefore, a large enough scaling factor does not affect the kNN search results [52] [14] [54]. For a point p , the process of scaling and rounding up the point cloud coordinates can be expressed as

$$p'_d = \lceil p_d \times scale \rceil \quad (5)$$

Non-negative integerization. Point cloud's integer coordinates are converted into *unsigned integers*. The bounding box is computed for point clouds, and the coordinate translating for each point is computed based on Equation (6), where the $high_d$ and low_d represent the upper and lower bound in the d -th dimension of bounding box. The Euclidean distance between two points remains the same if an offset is added to both, so the transition does not affect search results. Compared to the signed 2's complement data type, operating in *unsigned integer* data type can further simplify BDU's design, described in Section IV-C.

$$p''_d = p'_d + \left\lceil \frac{2^{\lceil \log_2(high_d - low_d) \rceil} - high_d - low_d}{2} \right\rceil, \forall d = 1, 2, 3 \quad (6)$$

Dimension-wise serialization The point's coordinate is serialized into dimension-wise bit flow. There are two steps of serialization. First, unnecessary bits are eliminated. After bit elimination, the bit width of the coordinate differs among the three dimensions. Specifically, each dimension d utilizes $\lceil \log_2(high_d - low_d) \rceil$ bits. Second, the point coordinate values are serialized in a dimension-wise manner. Figure 8 illustrates the serialization process for a point (17, 10, 4), which is serialized into a 12-bit flow. Each dimension has a different color. The serialization starts from MSB to LSB and alternates among the three dimensions, which matches the order of bit-serial distance computing. The black arrows indicate the serialization order in Figure 8. Additionally, a *dimension code flow* is used to identify the bit's dimension. Specifically, each bit needs a 2-bit *dimension code*, with 2'b01, 2'b10

Fig. 8. Example of dimension-wise serialization. A point positions at (17, 10, 4). After bit elimination, the length of coordinate values decreases from 6 bits to 5 bits, 4 bits, 3 bits for X, Y, Z dimensions, respectively. With serialization, a 12 bits point bit flow is generated.

Fig. 9. Example of storing 8 points (Point A-H) bit flows into SRAM. The width of SRAM is 8 bits.

and 2'b11 representing the X, Y and Z, respectively. In a specific kNN search kernel, the point cloud encoding mode and data width remain consistent for query and reference points. Consequently, the *dimension code flow* is shared across all points, resulting in negligible memory overhead.

C. Point-wise Data Layout

The conventional approach packages a single point within a fixed-width data structure and utilizes padding bits to ensure alignment of boundaries (i.e., padding to 64 bits). However, the padding bits lead to unnecessary on-chip and off-chip memory accesses. We propose a point-wise data layout that avoids the padding fields. As shown in Figure 9, multiple points' bit flow are aggregated. Instead of storing one point in an SRAM row, the point bit flow is stored in multiple columns of SRAM. In this way, the variable length of bit flow can be stored in the fixed-width SRAM without padding. Moreover, this mapping method is suitable for bit-serial computation, as it computes one bit per point per cycle.

D. Early Termination Mechanism

The bit-serial Euclidean distance computation mechanism exposes a new opportunity to terminate unnecessary computation, significantly reducing computation cost and on-chip memory access. Specifically, in the execution of bit-serial Euclidean distance computation between q and r , the partial distance $dist_m^2(q, r)$ gradually reaches the complete value

$Dist^2(q, r)$ as m increases from 1 to B . It becomes possible to terminate the computation promptly once confirming that r will never be the result of kNN. In this way, the remaining computation of r is reduced, and there is no need to load the rest of the bit flow data of r .

To achieve such goal, we propose a lower bound estimating method and an early termination mechanism. The lower bound estimation is based on the fact that the MSBs contribute more than the LSBs on the Euclidean distance result. For two given points q and r , the lower bound of the square Euclidean distance, denoted as $g_b^2(q, r)$ is

$$g_m^2(q, r) = \left(dist_m^2(q, r) - \sum_{d=1}^3 h_{d,m}(q, r) \right) \times 2^{2(B-m)} \quad (7)$$

$$h_{d,m}(q, r) = \begin{cases} 2 \times |f_{d,m}(q, r)| - 1, & f_{d,m}(q, r) \neq 0 \\ 0, & f_{d,m}(q, r) = 0 \end{cases}$$

As we can see, the estimated lower bound only relates to the $dist_m^2(q, r)$, $f_{d,m}(q, r)$, and $2(B - m)$, which can be easily obtained from the variables within bit-serial Euclidean distance computation. Appendix C shows the detailed derivation process.

With the aid of the lower bound estimation method, the early termination mechanism is as follows: in executing bit-serial distance computation, the lower bound is estimated and compared with the current k -th nearest point's distance. The computation is terminated when the lower bound exceeds the k -th nearest point's distance.

Figure 10 presents an example that corroborates the bit-serial Euclidean distance computation mechanism and illustrates the benefit of early termination. Without the early termination mechanism, the computation of the complete square Euclidean distance would require 8 cycles. The square Euclidean distance is 466. However, by leveraging the early termination mechanism, the Euclidean distance computation between q and r can be halted after 3 cycles, achieving 62.5% runtime reduction. This is because the estimated lower bound, 256, exceeds the current k -th $dist^2$, which is 100. Even if the complete distance is computed by another 5 cycles, the result is still greater than 100. Therefore, r will not be updated into the k nearest neighbor list.

E. Bit-serial K-Nearest Neighbor Search

Based on the bit-serial Euclidean distance computation mechanism and early termination mechanism, a bit-serial k -nearest neighbor search algorithm is proposed. The pseudocode is shown in Algorithm 1. As shown in lines 1-4, for a given query point q , it computes the Euclidean distance with every reference point. The detail of the *bitSerialCompute* function is shown in lines 6-14. This function starts by initializing some necessary variables. Then, it updates the $dist^2$ and *lowbound* using the Equations (4) and (7) in a bit-serial manner. The function processes one bit of q and r in each loop. The computation is terminated when the *lowbound* exceeds the kth_dist^2 , as shown in lines 11-12.

Fig. 10. Example of the bit-serial computation of square Euclidean distance and lower bound estimation between q and r . Assuming the query point q positions at (23,1) while the reference point r positions at (2,6) of the x-y coordinate system. Current k -th value of q is 100. The x dimension is encoded using 5 bits, while the y dimension is encoded using 3 bits. With the aid of the early terminated mechanism, the computation terminates at 3 cycles, reducing 62.5% runtime.

IV. BIT-SERIAL KNN ARCHITECTURE

In this section, a domain-specific bit-serial kNN accelerator is presented (Sec. IV-A). The accelerator exploits the massive parallelism of kNN search to improve performance (Sec. IV-B). Within the accelerator, the Bit-serial Distance Unit (BDU) performs the bit-serial Euclidean distance computation and leverages the early termination mechanism to reduce unnecessary computation (Sec. IV-C). Moreover, the topK array that supports arbitrary k is presented (Sec. IV-D). Finally, we discuss combining BitNN with the existing bit-parallel kNN accelerators (Sec. IV-E).

A. Accelerator Overview

The overview of the BitNN architecture is shown in Figure 11. It mainly consists of a BDU array, a query buffer, a reference buffer, a topK array and other components such as a control unit and DMA. BitNN has two AXI interfaces: one for external memory access and another for accelerator configuration. This design allows for easy integration of BitNN into larger systems.

The BDU array plays a key role in Euclidean distance computation. It consists of a set of Bit-serial Distance Units (BDUs), arranged as a two-dimensional mesh. Each BDU conducts the bit-serial distance computation between the given two points. Although the query and reference points are broadcasted to multiple BDUs, the narrow data bus will not

Algorithm 1: Bit-serial kNN Search (BKNS)

Input : Query Point q ; Reference Points R ; Topk K ; Bit flow length B
Output: K-Nearest Neighbor Points S ;

- 1 **foreach** point r of Reference Points R **do**
- 2 $dist^2 \leftarrow bitSerialCompute(q, r, kth_dist^2, B)$;
- 3 update topK result S with $dist^2$;
- 4 $kth_dist^2 \leftarrow current\ kth\ dist^2\ of\ S$;

5 **Function** bitSerialCompute(p, r, kth_dist^2, B)
Input : Query Point p ; Reference Point r ;
 k -th Square Euclidean distance kth_dist^2 ;
Bit Flow Length B
Output: square Euclidean Distance $dist^2$;

- 6 $b \leftarrow 1$; $dist^2 \leftarrow 0$; $f[0], f[1], f[2] \leftarrow 0$;
- 7 $lowbound \leftarrow 0$;
- 8 **while** $b \leq B$ **do**
- 9 update $dist^2, f[0], f[1], f[2]$ by Equation (4);
- 10 update $lowbound$ by Equation (7);
- 11 **if** $lowbound \geq kth_dist^2$ **then**
- 12 **return** $+\infty$;
- 13 $b \leftarrow b + 1$;

14 **return** $dist^2$;

Fig. 11. Architecture overview of BitNN.

increase the difficulty of ASIC physical design, such as place and route. When the distance calculation is completed, the BDU transmits the computed distance and the corresponding reference point's coordinate (reference point bit flow) to the topK array in a systolic manner.

The topK array has multiple topK units, each of which performs an iteration-based sort to find arbitrary k nearest points (described in Sec. IV-D). The FSM-based control unit configures the DMA, BDUs and topK array. The DRAM stores the query points, reference points, result data and metadata (i.e., the dimension code of the point cloud).

B. Parallel Execution of Bit-serial KNN Search

The BitNN accelerator performs the kNN search in parallel execution mode. The pseudo-code of parallel search is shown

Algorithm 2: Parallel Bit-serial kNN Search

Input : Query Points Q ; Reference Points R ;
Topk k ; Bit flow length B ; Query Buffer
Size Q_B , Reference Buffer Size R_B ;
BDU Array Shape (M, N)

Output: K-Nearest Neighbor Points S ;

```

1  $Q_N \leftarrow Capacity(Q_B, k, B)$ ;
2  $R_N \leftarrow Capacity(R_B, B)$ ;
3 for  $Q_{idx} = 0; Q_{idx} < Sizeof(Q); Q_{idx} += Q_N$  do
4   load  $Q_N$  query points to  $QueryBuf$ ;
5   for  $R_{idx} = 0; R_{idx} < Sizeof(R); R_{idx} += R_N$  do
6     load  $R_N$  reference points to  $ReferenceBuf$ ;
7     // loop unrolling, factor=  $N$ 
8     foreach point  $q$  in  $QueryBuf$  do
9       load  $q$  into local query registers;
10      if  $R_{idx} \neq 0$  then
11        load  $tmp$  topK into the topK array from
12         $QueryBuf$ ;
13        // loop unrolling, factor=  $M$ 
14        foreach point  $r$  in  $ReferenceBuf$  do
15          Bit-serial Computing and Sorting as the
16          Algorithm 1 (Line 3-5);
17        store  $tmp$  topK into  $QueryBuf$ ;

```

in Algorithm 2. The algorithm consists of four level loops.

In the initial stage, which is shown as Algorithm 2 lines 1-2, the algorithm computes the capacity for the query point and reference point within the constraint of the on-chip buffer.

For the first two level loops, as shown in Algorithm 2 lines 3-6, the query points Q_N are loaded into the query buffer by DMA. Then, all reference points are loaded into the reference buffer in batches of R_N points. When all reference points have been processed, the next Q_N query points are loaded into the query buffer. Then, the above processing is repeated until all query points are processed. The first two-level loop enables the BitNN to efficiently handle the arbitrary size of the point cloud within the capacity constraint of the on-chip buffer, which is a crucial consideration for hardware design.

For the last two level loops, in Algorithm 2 lines 7-13, the BDU array and topK array process query points and reference points loaded by the first two-level loop. The BDU array exploits both query point-level parallelism and reference point-level parallelism. It simultaneously processes N query points with M reference points. In Algorithm 2 lines 7-10, the query points are fetched from query buffer to local query registers, and temporary topK records are loaded into the topK array if necessary. Then, in Algorithm 2 lines 11-12, reference points are fed into the BDU array in M points parallel. The reference buffer only needs to provide M bits per cycle because each BDU only handles 1 bit of reference point per cycle, and the BDU, which is located in the same row, processes the same reference point. After N query points are processed with R_N reference points, temporary topK records are stored in the query buffer in a bit stream form. In the next iteration, subsequent N query points are acquired to repeat the above processing until all query points are processed.

Fig. 12. BDU component.

C. Bit-serial Distance Unit

The architecture of the BDU is illustrated in Figure 12. It comprises three components: square distance logics, lower bound logics and issue logics. The multiplication operations in Equations (4) and (7) can be implemented by left shift logics and multiplexers instead of general multipliers for less area and energy overhead.

Square distance logics compute the square Euclidean distance according to Equation (4). As shown in Figure 12, square distance logics take three inputs: query point bit flow (denoted as q , 1 bit), reference point bit flow (denoted as p , 1 bit) and dimension code flow (denoted as $code$, 2 bits). Only one negation block is employed because the coordinates are formatted in *unsigned integer* data type. The square distance logics generate the value of $dist_b^2(q, p)$, $f_{1,b}(q, p)$, $f_{2,b}(q, p)$ and $f_{3,b}(q, p)$. These results are stored in a 32-bit register and three 16-bit registers, respectively.

Lower bound logics compute the lower bound of $dist^2(q, p)$ based on Equation (7). As shown in Figure 12, the lower bound logics take two inputs: a 32-bit $kth dist^2$ from square distance logics and a left shift indicator (denoted as $2(B - b)$) from the control unit. Early termination is achieved by a comparator that checks whether the lower bound exceeds the current $kth dist^2$. Finally, the comparison result (denoted as $Terminate$) returns to the control unit.

Issue logics transmit the square distance and the reference point's coordinate (reference point bit flow) to the topK unit in a systolic manner. The reference point bit flow is restructured by shift registers.

D. Arbitrary K Mapping

The number of nearest neighbors varies among applications. To support arbitrary k nearest neighbors, we propose an iteration-based topK unit. As shown in Figure 13, the topK unit consists of a filter and several sort nodes. These sort nodes perform the insertion-based sorting (similar to [45]),

Fig. 13. The architecture of the topK unit.

which is optimized for streaming query and reference points to achieve high throughput. Although a single topK unit can only process one BDU’s computing result per cycle, it rarely becomes the performance bottleneck because most BDUs do not transmit the result when it meets the early termination condition. Moreover, a filter is incorporated into the topK unit, which can filter out the inputs whose square distance is less than or equal to the boundary value.

Assuming a topK unit has N sort nodes. For a particular kNN search task, the square distance of m -th nearest neighbor point is denoted as $Dist_m^2$, where $m \leq k$.

When $k \leq N$, the topK unit functions as a normal N -sorter. Each TopK unit receives streamed $\{dist^2, coord.\}$ data, performs an insertion-based sort to update the current topK result and return the k -th $dist^2$ value to the BDU array for early termination. To anchor the k -th $dist^2$ in the last node, the first $N - k$ node’s $dist^2$ registers are padded with 0.

When $k > N$, the topK unit identifies the k nearest points in $\lceil \frac{k}{N} \rceil$ iterations. Specifically, in the first iteration, the topK unit functions as a normal N -sorter. At the end of the iteration, the N neighbor points (from top1 to topN) are stored sequentially in these N sorted nodes in order from smallest to largest. Then, the last sort node’s $dist^2$ value, which is $Dist_N^2$, is set to the boundary register in the filter. In the next iteration, the reference points are streamed into the BDU array again. The neighbor points found in the first iteration will be filtered out because their distance value is less or equal to the boundary value. When all reference points are processed, the topK unit identifies points with the $(N + 1)$ -th to $(2 \times N)$ -th minimum distance. Then, the last node’s $dist^2$ value, which is $Dist_{2N}^2$, is set to the boundary register. This iteration continues until all k nearest neighbors have been found.

Since the value of k in point cloud applications is typically small (≤ 64), the topK unit, composed of 16 sort nodes, can find the required neighbor points within 4 iterations ($k \leq 64$). Experiments show that, on average, our design is $1.58 \times$ faster than the merge sort-based topK engine proposed in PointAcc [27] with the same parallelism. In theory, when $k > N$, the iteration-based topK mechanism may overlook some actual neighbor points if the distances between the query point and multiple reference points equal the boundary

Fig. 14. (a) The architecture of the Bit-serial ParallelINN. The detail of the Bit-Parallel region is described in [9]. (b) The architecture of the serializer and deserializer components.

value. Nevertheless, the probability of this occurrence is rare. Experimental results demonstrate that it leads to less than a 0.3% degradation in search accuracy on the KITTI dataset.

E. Combination with Existing Bit-Parallel Accelerators

This paper primarily focuses on the operation-level optimization technique, which is orthogonal to existing techniques that exploit the algorithm and architecture-level optimization. Existing point cloud kNN accelerators employ multiple Euclidean distance computation units as a computing array, which can be easily replaced by the bit-serial computing architecture. Take the state-of-the-art accelerator, ParallelINN [9], as an example. The accelerator mainly comprises 8 branch construction engines and 8 branch search engines. The former engines partition the point cloud into multiple small regions using an octree-based approach and assign each query point to a specific region. The latter engines perform the Euclidean distance and topK operations for every query point. Each query point only searches the neighbor points within a single region, resulting in an approximate search result. As shown in Figure 14, to combine the bit-serial technique into ParallelINN, the overall accelerator is separated into two regions: the bit-parallel construction region and the bit-serial search region. Moreover, several serialization and deserialization components are employed to connect these two regions. Specifically, the construction engines are retained, while the search engines are replaced by several BDU arrays and topK arrays. In this way, the existing optimization techniques can be reused, such as search space reduction, query point aggregation, fine-grained pipeline and HBM memory mapping.

Furthermore, the BitNN architecture can be effectively employed for other Euclidean distance-based applications, such as radius search [12], farthest point sampling [21]. For instance, the radius search targets to find points located within a predetermined distance (denoted as r). To perform radius search, the BDU’s inputs ($kth dist^2$) are configured to r^2 .

V. EXPERIMENT

A. Evaluation Setup

Benchmarks. We perform evaluations on four widely used point cloud datasets. As shown in Table II, we pick

TABLE II
EVALUATED BENCHMARKS.

Dataset	Scene	Sensor	Accuracy	# of points
KITTI [17]	Outdoor	LiDAR	$10^{-2} m$	75,000
Waymo [44]	Outdoor	LiDAR	$10^{-3} m$	90,000
ICL-NUIM [10]	Indoor	3D scanner	$10^{-4} m$	380,000
SemanticKITTI [6]	Outdoor	LiDAR	$10^{-2} m$	460,000

KITTI [17], Waymo [44], augmented ICL-NUIM [10] and SemanticKITTI [6] datasets. The selected dataset is comprehensive and realistic, covering a diverse array of sizes, accuracies, and modalities for input point clouds. We fuse multiple point clouds from the SemanticKITTI dataset to create a series of large point clouds. The average point cloud size is 460,000. This consolidated dataset is utilized to simulate workloads associated with the state-of-the-art LiDAR [37]. As mentioned in Section III-B, we set the *scale* to 100, 1000, 10000 and 100 for the KITTI, Waymo, ICL-NUIM and SemanticKITTI datasets, respectively, based on the sensors’ accuracy. As a common practice [9] [36], the ground points of the KITTI, Waymo and SemanticKITTI datasets are removed because they are non-informative. Following previous works [9] [43] [34], k is set to 5.

Baselines. We adopt two kinds of hardware as evaluation baselines: exact search and approximate search. The hardware parameters are shown in Table III.

Linear: For the exact kNN search, we set a linear search accelerator to carry out the brute-force search. It directly calculates distance with all the reference points to find the k neighbor points. The accelerator has 16 computing units, each of which carries out bit-parallel square distance computing and topK sorting. The accelerator is well optimized based on previous works [36] [34], such as ping-pong buffer and query-level parallelism for fair comparison. The DRAM parameters are modeled based on Micron’s 8GB DDR4-2400 according to its datasheet [22]. This representation reflects the embedded system scenario, such as emerging mobile SoCs.

ParallelNN: For the approximate kNN search, we use ParallelNN [9] as the baseline accelerator, which is the state-of-the-art bit-parallel kNN search architecture. ParallelNN is an efficient HBM-based architecture. It couples multi-channel HBM to provide large external bandwidth. ParallelNN has 8 parallel branches, each of which has 16 computing units. As mentioned in Section IV-E, for a given query point, it only searches neighbor points within a small region, resulting in an approximate search result.

Hardware Implementation. We design two hardware accelerators named BitNN and Bit-serial ParallelNN, corresponding to the Linear and ParallelNN architecture in baseline to evaluate the bit-serial technologies fully.

BitNN: BitNN consists of 1024 BDUs, organized in a topology of 16×64 . BitNN can process 16 query points simultaneously, which is the same as the Linear and one branch of ParallelNN. In terms of the reference point par-

TABLE III
EVALUATED ASIC PLATFORMS.

Chip	Exact search		Approximate search	
	Linear	BitNN	ParallelNN	Bit-serial ParallelNN
Computing Pattern	Bit-parallel	Bit-serial	Bit-parallel	Bit-serial
Point per bits	Static (64)	Dynamic	Static (64)	Dynamic
Number of Computing Unit	16	16×64	16 per branch 8 branches	16×64 per branch 8 branches
Query point Parallelism	16	16	16 per branch	16 per branch
Reference point Parallelism	1	64	1 per branch	64 per branch
DRAM Bandwidth	DDR4-2400 19.2GB/s		HBM2 256GB/s	
SRAM	256KB			
Frequency	1 GHz			
Technology	45 nm			

allelism, the BitNN’s total parallelism is $64 \times$ larger than that of the baselines. However, it is fair because the bit-parallel computing unit consumes one reference point (64 bits) per cycle. In contrast, the bit-serial computing unit consumes only one bit of the reference point per cycle. The topK array comprises 16 topK units, each of which contains 10 sorting nodes. The BitNN has a total on-chip SRAM of 256 KB. Both the query buffer and reference buffer occupy 128 KB.

Bit-serial ParallelNN: We apply the bit-serial techniques to ParallelNN and conduct an accelerator named Bit-serial ParallelNN to evaluate the effort of bit-serial techniques. The primary distinction between ParallelNN and Bit-serial ParallelNN lies in the search component. In Bit-serial ParallelNN, we replace the original bit-parallel search engines in the ParallelNN accelerator with the BDU array and topK array, as described in Section IV-E. Figure 14 shows the architecture of Bit-serial ParallelNN accelerator. The on-chip memory, frequency, technology and DRAM² are configured to be the same for a fair comparison.

Experimental Methodology. We implement accelerators using Verilog and verify the design through RTL simulations. The hardwares are synthesized by Synopsys Design Compiler in a 45 nm process technology. The power is estimated using Synopsys PrimeTimePX by annotating the gate-level switching activity. The memory compiler generates the SRAMs [19]. We utilize DRAMsim3 [25] to model the DRAM behaviors and measure the DRAM energy consumption. We employ OpenROAD [2], an open-source RTL-to-GDS tool, to run ASIC flow till place-and-route (PnR) for comprehensive evaluation.

B. Performance and Power Efficiency

Figure 15 presents the performance benefit of BitNN on four workloads under exact and approximate search. Specifically, for exact search, BitNN achieves a speedup of $6.4 \times$, $6.0 \times$,

²We assume that HBM2 is available because the accelerator is being integrated into an SoC that would otherwise have HBM2.

Fig. 15. Performance improvement over the baselines on four workloads.

Fig. 16. Power efficiency improvement over the baselines on four workloads.

3.7 \times and 6.6 \times on four workloads, respectively, compared to the bit-parallel linear architecture. For approximate search, the Bit-serial ParallelNN achieves a speedup of 4.4 \times , 3.0 \times , 2.6 \times and 4.1 \times on four workloads, respectively, compared to the state-of-the-art bit-parallel ParallelNN. The performance improvement can be attributed to the massive parallelism of BitNN’s BDU array and the early termination mechanism, which will be further analyzed in Section V-E.

Figure 16 illustrates the power efficiency of BitNN on four workloads. BitNN improves power efficiency by 3.6 \times , 3.3 \times , 2.1 \times and 2.5 \times compared to the bit-parallel linear accelerator on four workloads, respectively. Bit-serial ParallelNN improves power efficiency by 2.9 \times , 1.9 \times , 1.7 \times and 2.7 \times compared to the bit-parallel ParallelNN on four workloads, respectively. The power efficiency improvement is mainly attributed to the lightweight bit-serial computation logics and the reduction of on-chip/off-chip memory accesses. Specifically, BitNN reduces DRAM accesses by 66% and SRAM accesses by 84% on KITT workloads. This reduction is due to the dimension-wise point cloud encoding and the early termination mechanism, which will be further analyzed in Section V-D.

C. Area and Energy Breakdown

The BitNN and Linear architectures are modeled using the 45nm library for consistency. Figure 17 depicts the BitNN’s ASIC layout. The total area required is 7.21 mm^2 , compared to 5.41 mm^2 in the Linear architecture, resulting in an overhead of 33.2%. The area breakdown is shown in Table IV. The on-chip buffers are the predominant contributor to the area footprint. As for the computing components, the synthesis report shows that 1024 BDUs in BitNN increase the area by 218.6% compared to Linear’s 16 distance units. Although the BDU array raises the area overhead, the overall increase of the

TABLE IV
AREA ANALYSIS

Module	Area(μm^2)	Area(%)
BDU array (1024 BDUs)	2713.9k	37.6%
TopK array (16 topK units)	189.4k	2.6%
On-chip SRAM (256 KB)	4214.0k	58.4%
DMA (8 channels)	91.1k	1.3%
Controller	1.8k	0.1%
Total	7210.4k	100%

Fig. 17. The post PnR floor-plan diagram of BitNN (no RAMs). Fig. 18. Energy breakdown of BitNN on KITT benchmark.

overall chip area is only 33.2% because the on-chip memory takes up a significant portion of the chip area. Meanwhile, the serializer and deserializer components of the Bit-serial ParallelNN are evaluated, which take 0.026 mm^2 and 0.011 mm^2 , respectively, raising less than 1% area overhead.

Figure 18 breaks down the energy consumption of BitNN running 5NN on KITT dataset. BitNN takes 16.45 mJ in total. Computing logic covers 64.5% of the total energy, while SRAM and DRAM access costs account for 20.7% and 14.1% of the total energy, respectively. While the power consumption of a single topK unit (388 μW) exceeds that of a single BDU (189 μW), the overall energy consumption of the topK array remains minimal. This discrepancy arises because the number of topK units in the topK array is only 1/64th of the number of BDUs. Although each topK unit is capable of processing only one BDU’s computing result per cycle, it seldom becomes a performance bottleneck due to the early termination condition in BDUs, which prevents the transmission of results when met. The increased latency from blocking topK units amounts to only 0.13 ms (0.3% of the total runtime) in the KITT benchmark.

D. Memory Accesses

BitNN achieves reducing both on-chip and off-chip memory access. Figure 19 depicts the memory accesses associated with four workloads during the exact search. On average, BitNN achieves a reduction of 70.6% in on-chip memory access and 55.4% in external memory access, leading to a further decrease in energy consumption. The reduction in memory access is attributed to two factors.

First, the dimension-wise point cloud encoding method effectively compresses the point cloud. In contrast to traditional point cloud kNN accelerators, which generally employ a fixed

Fig. 19. On-chip and off-chip memory access of four workloads.

Fig. 20. Performance sensitivity analysis of four workloads.

64-bit representation for each point, BitNN dynamically adjust the bit width on a per-dimension basis. For instance, KITTI point clouds’ geometric information is encoded using 14, 14 and 9 bits for three dimensions, resulting in a total bit width of 37 and a 42.2% reduction in point cloud size. The encoding method eliminates the need for storing unnecessary padding bits in off-chip memory, thereby improving the utilization of the expensive off-chip memory bandwidth.

Secondly, the early termination mechanism serves to minimize on-chip memory accesses. The point data are loaded to the BDU array bit-by-bit. When the termination condition is satisfied in all BDUs, the remaining bits of the current point are skipped, leading to a notable reduction in SRAM access.

E. Ablation Study

Figure 20 demonstrates the efficacy of the proposed approach on four datasets for exact and approximate search. The accelerator, which only utilizes bit-serial computing, achieves a speedup of $1.54\times$ and $2.18\times$ compared to the baselines. Without the early termination mechanism, the execution time scales linearly with the bit length of the point cloud encoding.

Moreover, the early termination mechanism significantly improves performance. Figure 21 is a histogram of the percentage of computation cycles for four datasets. As we can see, most points do not require complete computation. On average, BitNN takes 10.1, 10.7, 17.4 and 9.7 cycles per point for exact search on four datasets, significantly reducing computation cost. Specifically, the distribution reveals two prominent peaks. The first peak falls within the 3-18 cycles range, indicating that these points meet the early termination condition and thus do not require further access to the remaining point bits. In particular, 4.5% of Euclidean distance computations are terminated within 4 cycles on KITTI dataset, reducing about

Fig. 21. The computing cycles distribution of four workloads.

Fig. 22. Latency increases with varying number of nearest neighbors for BitNN architecture.

90% computation cycles. The second peak occurs at the end of the abscissa. This is because the BDU is required to load the entire point data to compute the Euclidean distance completely for updating k nearest neighbor points. We break the runtime of BitNN and observe that the BDU array remains active for most execution time, while the topK array is activated for less than 5% of execution time.

F. Hardware Sensitivity Analysis

Number of Nearest Neighbor. Figure 22 shows the latency with varying numbers of nearest neighbor points. An increase from 1NN to 10NN results in a slight 2% rise in the runtime of BitNN. This is because the larger k will subsequently increase the early termination threshold, making it more challenging to meet the early termination condition.

Number of BDUs. Figure 23 illustrates the evaluation of BitNN with different numbers and shapes of BDUs. With an increase in BDUs from 64 to 4096, the runtime decreases from 729ms to 14.5ms. Initially, the increase of BDUs leads to a near-linear improvement in performance. This trend diminishes as more BDUs are employed because meeting the early termination condition in all BDUs becomes more difficult.

Fig. 23. Performance and power sensitivity to the various BDU array size under KITTI dataset.

VI. RELATED WORK

Point cloud kNN search. point cloud kNN search is an important kernel for point cloud processing. Previous works have proposed various optimizations for CPUs [12] and GPUs [4] [13] [26]. To achieve high performance and energy efficiency, there is increasing interest in accelerating kNN on customized hardware accelerators. Recently, several partition-based accelerators have been proposed, such as QuickNN [36], ParallelNN [9]. They split the point cloud into multiple buckets via KD-tree [36] [48] [15], octree [9] and voxel [50]. Then, they design approximate search algorithms to reduce the search space by only searching the neighbor points within a small region. Saikia et al. [40] and Mu et al. [31] exploit the PIM-based kNN accelerator. ParallelNN [9] and CHIP-KNNv2 [28] couple the architecture with HBM memory. Kaul et al. [24] propose an energy efficiency kNN accelerator with adaptive precision. However, it only supports up to 128 candidate points and has to perform bit-parallel subtraction before adaptive precision multiplication. K-D Bonsai [12] is an ISA extension that compresses the point cloud, reducing the memory usage during radius search. PointAcc [27] proposes a programmable pipeline architecture. However, existing works compute the Euclidean distance in a bit-parallel manner. The data type and data width are fixed. Unlike prior accelerators, BitNN proposes the bit-serial computing manner and takes advantage of the massive bit-level parallelism and early termination mechanism to improve performance. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work that extends the bit-serial computation on kNN for 3D point clouds.

Bit-serial computation. BSC is a prevailing computation method for varying-precision applications. Several works use BSC for DNN, exploiting the bit-level sparsity [49] [3] [11] and varying neuron precision [23] [42] [39]. However, existing bit-serial DNN accelerators concentrate on inner-product computing operations and cannot directly apply to the Euclidean distance for 3D point clouds. Recently, bit-serial SIMD Processing-In-Memory receives a considerable amount of attention [35] [41] [20] [47]. However, they only support synthesizing basic logic operations (e.g. AND/OR/NOT).

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces a bit-serial accelerator to enhance the performance efficiency for kNN search for 3D point clouds. We extend the bit-serial computing technique to enable Euclidean distance computations. Additionally, we propose an early termination mechanism to eliminate unnecessary computations at the bit level. To further optimize the hardware, we incorporate various schemes, including bit-level parallelism and arbitrary k mapping. BitNN achieves $4.4 \times$ speedup and $2.9 \times$ power efficiency improvement compared to the current state-of-the-art architecture.

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APPENDIX

We first give the detailed definition of the metrics $dist_m^2(q, r)$ and $f_m(q, r)$, then show the proof process of Equations (3), (4), and (7).

A. Definition of $dist_m^2(q, r)$ and $f_{d,m}(q, r)$

$dist_m^2(q, r)$: the square distance of point q and r , where q and r 's coordinate values only keep most significant m bits. When $m = 0$, $d_m^2(q, r) = 0$.

$f_{d,m}(q, r)$: the subtraction of the coordinate values in the d -th dimension between point q and r , where q and r 's coordinate values only keep most significant m bits. When $m = 0$, $f_{d,m}(q, r) = 0$.

e.g., Take the case in Figure 7 as an example. Two points, q and r , is located at 18 and 9, respectively. Their binary encodings are $10010_{(2)}$ and $01001_{(2)}$. Thus, $f_{1,3}(q, r)$ represents the subtraction of the most significant 3 bits of q , which is $100_{(2)}$, and the most significant 3 bits of r , which is $010_{(2)}$. Therefore, the value of $f_{1,3}(q, r) = 4 - 2 = 2$.

Lemma 1. For two points (q and r) whose bit width of the coordinate value is B , when $m > 0$, the $f_{d,m}(q, r)$ can be computed based on the $f_{d,m-1}(q, r)$.

$$f_{d,m}(q, r) = 2 \times f_{d,m-1}(q, r) + q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m} \quad (8)$$

Proof. Based on the definition, when $m > 0$, $f_{d,m}(q, r)$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} q_{d,b} \times 2^{b-(B-m)} - \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} r_{d,b} \times 2^{b-(B-m)} \\
&= \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times 2^{b-(B-m)} \\
&= q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m} + \sum_{b=B-m+1}^{B-1} (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times 2^{b-(B-m)} \\
&= q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m} + 2 \times \sum_{b=B-m+1}^{B-1} (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times 2^{b-(B-m)-1} \\
&= q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m} + 2 \times f_{d,m-1}(q, r)
\end{aligned}$$

B. The Bit-serial Computation of Square Euclidean Distance

Lemma 2. For a natural number of P , the square of P equals $\sum_{b=0}^{B-1} P_b^2 + 2 \times \sum_{b=0}^{B-1} \sum_{b'=b+1}^{B-1} P_b \times P_{b'} \times 2^{b+b'}$, where B is the bit width of P .

Proof. Based on the definition, P equals $\sum_{b=0}^{B-1} P_b \times 2^b$. Thus, P^2 is rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned}
P^2 &= \left(\sum_{b=0}^{B-1} P_b \times 2^b \right)^2 \\
&= \left(\sum_{b=0}^{B-1} P_b \times 2^b \right) \times \left(\sum_{b'=0}^{B-1} P_{b'} \times 2^{b'} \right) \quad (9) \\
&= \sum_{b=0}^{B-1} \sum_{b'=0}^{B-1} P_b \times P_{b'} \times 2^{b+b'}
\end{aligned}$$

The Equation (9) can be organized as the sum of B^2 items:

$$\begin{pmatrix}
\underline{P_0 P_0 * 2^0} & P_0 P_1 * 2^1 & P_0 P_2 * 2^2 & \dots & P_0 P_{B-1} * 2^{B-1} \\
P_1 P_0 * 2^1 & \underline{P_1 P_1 * 2^2} & P_1 P_2 * 2^3 & \dots & P_1 P_{B-1} * 2^B \\
P_2 P_0 * 2^2 & P_2 P_1 * 2^3 & \underline{P_2 P_2 * 2^4} & \dots & P_2 P_{B-1} * 2^{B+1} \\
\dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\
P_{B-1} P_0 * 2^{B-1} & P_{B-1} P_1 * 2^B & P_{B-1} P_2 * 2^{B+1} & \dots & \underline{P_{B-1}^2 * 2^{2(B-1)}}
\end{pmatrix}$$

These B^2 products can be split into three parts: the diagonal part, the upper triangular part and the lower triangular part. The diagonal part is marked with a wavy underline, such as $P_0 P_0 * 2^0$, $P_1 P_1 * 2^2$. The triangular parts are drawn with different colors.

The Equation (9) can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned}
P^2 &= \sum_{b=0}^{B-1} P_b^2 \times 2^{2b} + \sum_{b=0}^{B-1} \sum_{b'=b+1}^{B-1} P_b \times P_{b'} \times 2^{b+b'} + \\
&\quad \sum_{b=1}^{B-1} \sum_{b'=0}^{b-1} P_b \times P_{b'} \times 2^{b+b'}
\end{aligned}$$

Due to the commutative law of multiplication, the items within triangular parts that are drawn in the same colors are equal. Therefore, the sum of the upper triangular part is equal to the sum of the lower triangular part.

The Equation (10) can be further converted as:

$$P^2 = \sum_{b=0}^{B-1} P_b^2 \times 2^{2b} + 2 \times \sum_{b=0}^{B-1} \sum_{b'=b+1}^{B-1} P_b \times P_{b'} \times 2^{b+b'}$$

Theorem 1. The $dist_m^2(q, r)$ can be computed in a bit-serial manner. Assume B is the bit width of the point's coordinate value.

$$\begin{aligned}
dist_m^2(q, r) &= 2^{2(m-B)} \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} 2^{2b} \left[\sum_{d=1}^3 [(q_{d,b} - r_{d,b})^2 + \right. \\
&\quad \left. 4 \times (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times f_{d,B-b-1}(q, r) \right] \quad (10)
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Based on the definition, the $dist_m^2(q, r)$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
dist_m^2(q, r) &= \sum_{d=1}^3 \left[\sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} q_{d,b} \times 2^{b+m-B} - \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} r_{d,b} \times 2^{b+m-B} \right]^2 \\
&= \sum_{d=1}^3 \left[\sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times 2^{b+m-B} \right]^2
\end{aligned}$$

Convert the $\left[\sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times 2^{b+m-B} \right]^2$ using Lemma

2. Thus, the $dist_m^2(q, r)$ can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{d=1}^3 \left[\sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b})^2 \times 2^{2b+2(m-B)} + \right. \\
&\quad \left. 2 \times \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} \sum_{b'=b+1}^{B-1} [(q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times (q_{d,b'} - r_{d,b'}) \times 2^{b+b'+2(m-B)}] \right]
\end{aligned}$$

The value of $2^{2(m-B)}$ is extracted from the sum of the diagonal and the sum of the upper triangular part. Then, the $dist_m^2(q, r)$ can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
&= 2^{2(m-B)} \times \sum_{d=1}^3 \left[\sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b})^2 \times 2^{2b} + 2 \times \right. \\
&\quad \left. \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} \sum_{b'=b+1}^{B-1} [(q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times (q_{d,b'} - r_{d,b'}) \times 2^{b+b'}] \right]
\end{aligned}$$

The value of 2^{2b} is extracted from the sum of the diagonal and the sum of the upper triangular part. The $dist_m^2(q, r)$ can be converted to:

$$\begin{aligned}
&= 2^{2(m-B)} \times \sum_{d=1}^3 \left[\sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} 2^{2b} \times (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b})^2 + \right. \\
&\quad \left. 2 \times \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} 2^{2b} \sum_{b'=b+1}^{B-1} (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times (q_{d,b'} - r_{d,b'}) \times 2^{b'-b} \right] \\
&= 2^{2(m-B)} \times \sum_{d=1}^3 \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} 2^{2b} \left[(q_{d,b} - r_{d,b})^2 + \right. \\
&\quad \left. 2 \times (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times \sum_{b'=b+1}^{B-1} (q_{d,b'} - r_{d,b'}) \times 2^{b'-b} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

The value of 2 is extracted from the sum of the upper triangular part. The $dist_m^2(q, r)$ can be written as:

$$= 2^{2(m-B)} \times \sum_{d=1}^3 \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} 2^{2b} \left[(q_{d,b} - r_{d,b})^2 + 4 \times (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times \sum_{b'=b+1}^{B-1} (q_{d,b'} - r_{d,b'}) \times 2^{b'-b-1} \right]$$

Based on the definition of $f_{d,m}(q, r)$, the $\sum_{b'=b+1}^{B-1} (q_{d,b'} - r_{d,b'}) \times 2^{b'-b-1}$ is equal to $f_{d,B-b-1}(q, r)$. The $dist_m^2(q, r)$ can be written as:

$$= 2^{2(m-B)} \times \sum_{d=1}^3 \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} 2^{2b} \left[(q_{d,b} - r_{d,b})^2 + 4 \times (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times f_{d,B-b-1}(q, r) \right]$$

The terms $\sum_{d=1}^3$ and $\sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} 2^{2b}$ is reordered. The $dist_m^2(q, r)$ can be written as:

$$= 2^{2(m-B)} \times \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} 2^{2b} \sum_{d=1}^3 \left[(q_{d,b} - r_{d,b})^2 + 4 \times (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times f_{d,B-b-1}(q, r) \right]$$

Corollary 1. For two points (q and r) whose bit width of the coordinate value is B . When $m > 0$, the $dist_m^2(q, r)$ can be computed by:

$$\begin{aligned} dist_m^2(q, r) &= \underbrace{dist_{m-1}^2(q, r)}_{\ll 2} + \underbrace{\sum_{d=1}^3 [(q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m})^2]}_{\ll 2} + \underbrace{\sum_{d=1}^3 [(q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m}) \times f_{d,m-1}(q, r)]}_{\ll 2} \\ f_{d,m}(q, r) &= f_{d,m-1}(q, r) \ll 1 + (q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m}) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Proof. The $f_{d,m}(q, r)$ of Equation (11) has been proofed by Lemma 1. For $dist_m^2(q, r)$, we first define a metric, denoted as $T_m(q, r)$, where

$$\begin{aligned} T_m(q, r) &= \frac{dist_m^2(q, r)}{2^{2(m-B)}} \\ &= \sum_{b=B-m}^{B-1} 2^{2b} \sum_{d=1}^3 \left[(q_{d,b} - r_{d,b})^2 + 4 \times (q_{d,b} - r_{d,b}) \times f_{d,B-b-1}(q, r) \right] \end{aligned}$$

When $m > 1$, $T_m(q, r) - T_{m-1}(q, r)$ is as follow

$$\begin{aligned} &T_m(q, r) - T_{m-1}(q, r) \\ &= \frac{dist_m^2(q, r)}{2^{2(m-B)}} - \frac{dist_{m-1}^2(q, r)}{2^{2(m-B-1)}} \\ &= 2^{2(B-m)} \times \sum_{d=1}^3 \left[(q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m})^2 + 4 \times (q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m}) \times f_{d,m-1}(q, r) \right] \\ &= 2^{2(B-m)} \times \left[\sum_{d=1}^3 [(q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m})^2] + 4 \times \sum_{d=1}^3 [(q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m}) \times f_{d,m-1}(q, r)] \right] \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $T_m(q, r)$ can be computed as follow

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dist_m^2(q, r)}{2^{2(m-B)}} &= \frac{dist_{m-1}^2(q, r)}{2^{2(m-B-1)}} + 2^{2(B-m)} \times \left[\sum_{d=1}^3 [(q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m})^2] + 4 \times \sum_{d=1}^3 [(q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m}) \times f_{d,m-1}(q, r)] \right] \end{aligned}$$

The value of $2^{2(m-B)}$ is multiplied at both sides. $dist_m^2(q, r)$ can be converted as:

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{dist_{m-1}^2(q, r)}{2^{2(m-B)} \times 2^{-2}} \times \cancel{2^{2(m-B)}} + \cancel{2^{2(B-m)}} \times \cancel{2^{2(m-B)}} \times \left[\sum_{d=1}^3 [(q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m})^2] + 4 \times \sum_{d=1}^3 [(q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m}) \times f_{d,m-1}(q, r)] \right] \\ &= \underbrace{dist_{m-1}^2(q, r)}_{\ll 2} + \sum_{d=1}^3 \underbrace{[(q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m})^2]}_{\ll 2} + \sum_{d=1}^3 \underbrace{[(q_{d,B-m} - r_{d,B-m}) \times f_{d,m-1}(q, r)]}_{\ll 2} \end{aligned}$$

C. The Lower Bound of the Square Euclidean Distance

First, we give the detail definition of the metric $g_m^2(q, r)$, then we discuss how to calculate the lower bound of $dist_B^2(q, r)$ for a single dimension. Finally, we show how to compute the lower bound for three dimensions. Assume the bit length of the coordinates is B .

$g_m^2(q, r)$: the estimated lower bound of the square distance of point q and r , where only most significant m bits of q and r are known.

Lemma 3. For a single dimension, when $m > 0$,

$$dist_B^2(q, r) \geq [f_{1,m}(q, r)^2 - h_{1,m}(q, r)] \ll 2(B-m)$$

where

$$h_{d,m}(q,r) = \begin{cases} 2 \times |f_{d,m}(q,r)| - 1, & f_{d,m}(q,r) \neq 0 \\ 0, & f_{d,m}(q,r) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Proof. There are three conditions based on the value of $f_{1,m}(q,r)$.

When $f_{1,m}(q,r) > 0$, the worst case for $dist_B^2(q,r)$ is that the q 's last significant $B - m$ bits are 0, while r 's last significant $B - m$ bits are 1. So that, the minimum value of the square Euclidean distance is as follow

$$\begin{aligned} dist_B^2(q,r) &\geq [f_{1,m}(q,r) \times 2^{B-m} + 0 - (2^{B-m} - 1)]^2 \\ &= [(f_{1,m}(q,r) - 1) \times 2^{B-m} + 1]^2 \\ &> [(f_{1,m}(q,r) - 1) \times 2^{B-m}]^2 \\ &= [(f_{1,m}(q,r)^2 - 2 \times f_{1,m}(q,r) + 1)] \times 2^{2(B-m)} \\ &= [f_{1,m}(q,r)^2 - h_{1,m}(q,r)] \ll 2(B-m) \end{aligned}$$

When $f_{1,m}(q,r) < 0$, the worst case for $dist_B^2(q,r)$ is that the q 's last significant $B - m$ bits are 1, while r 's last significant $B - m$ bits are 0. So that, the minimum value of the square Euclidean distance is as follow

$$\begin{aligned} dist_B^2(q,r) &\geq [f_{1,m}(q,r) \times 2^{B-m} + (2^{B-m} - 1) - 0]^2 \\ &= [(f_{1,m}(q,r) + 1) \times 2^{B-m} - 1]^2 \\ &> [(f_{1,m}(q,r) + 1) \times 2^{B-m}]^2 \\ &= [(f_{1,m}(q,r)^2 + 2 \times f_{1,m}(q,r) + 1)] \times 2^{2(B-m)} \\ &= [f_{1,m}(q,r)^2 - h_{1,m}(q,r)] \ll 2(B-m) \end{aligned}$$

When $f_{1,m}(q,r) = 0$, the worst case for $dist_B^2(q,r)$ is that the q is equal to r . As a result, the minimum value of square Euclidean distance is as follow

$$\begin{aligned} dist_B^2(q,r) &\geq 0 \\ &= (f_{1,m}(q,r)^2 - 0) \ll 2(B-m) \\ &= [f_{1,m}(q,r)^2 - h_{1,m}(q,r)] \ll 2(B-m) \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2. For two given points q and r , the lower bound of the $dist_B^2(q,r)$ is the sum of the lower bound for each dimension. When $m > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} dist_B^2(q,r) &\geq \sum_{d=1}^3 (f_{d,m}(q,r)^2 - h_{d,m}(q,r)) \ll 2(B-m) \\ &= \left(\sum_{d=1}^3 f_{d,m}(q,r)^2 - \sum_{d=1}^3 h_{d,m}(q,r) \right) \ll 2(B-m) \\ &= (dist_m^2(q,r) - \sum_{d=1}^3 h_{d,m}(q,r)) \ll 2(B-m) \\ &= g_m^2(q,r) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

It is worth noting that the estimated lower bound of $dist_B^2(q,r)$ in Corollary 2 is smaller than the actual lower

bound. However, it is more hardware-friendly than the actual lower bound, which requires more shifter and addition operations.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. 3D, "Artec 3d micro ii 3d scanner," <https://www.artec3d.com/portable-3d-scanners/artec-micro>, 2023.
- [2] T. Ajayi, D. Blaauw, T. Chan, C. Cheng, V. Chhabria, D. Choo, M. Coltella, S. Dobre, R. Dreslinski, M. Fogaça *et al.*, "Openroad: Toward a self-driving, open-source digital layout implementation tool chain," *Proc. GOMACTECH*, pp. 1105–1110, 2019.
- [3] J. Albericio, A. Delmás, P. Judd, S. Sharify, G. O'Leary, R. Genov, and A. Moshovos, "Bit-pragmatic deep neural network computing," in *Proceedings of the 50th Annual IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Microarchitecture (MICRO)*, 2017, pp. 382–394.
- [4] R. J. Barrientos, J. I. Gómez, C. Tenllado, M. P. Matias, and M. Marin, "knn query processing in metric spaces using gpus," in *Proceedings of the 17th European Conference on Parallel Processing (Euro-Par)*, 2011, pp. 380–392.
- [5] P. H. Becker, J. M. Arnau, and A. González, "Demystifying power and performance bottlenecks in autonomous driving systems," in *Proceedings of IEEE International Symposium on Workload Characterization (IISWC)*, 2020, pp. 205–215.
- [6] J. Behley, M. Garbade, A. Milioto, J. Quenzel, S. Behnke, C. Stachniss, and J. Gall, "Semantickitti: A dataset for semantic scene understanding of lidar sequences," in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision (ICCV)*, 2019, pp. 9297–9307.
- [7] P. J. Besl and N. D. McKay, "Method for registration of 3-d shapes," in *Sensor fusion IV: control paradigms and data structures*, vol. 1611, 1992, pp. 586–606.
- [8] C. Chen, G. Li, R. Xu, T. Chen, M. Wang, and L. Lin, "Clusternet: Deep hierarchical cluster network with rigorously rotation-invariant representation for point cloud analysis," in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (CVPR)*, 2019, pp. 4994–5002.
- [9] F. Chen, R. Ying, J. Xue, F. Wen, and P. Liu, "Parallelnn: A parallel octree-based nearest neighbor search accelerator for 3d point clouds," in *Proceedings of IEEE International Symposium on High-Performance Computer Architecture (HPCA)*, 2023, pp. 403–414.
- [10] S. Choi, Q.-Y. Zhou, and V. Koltun, "Robust reconstruction of indoor scenes," in *Proceedings of IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2015.
- [11] A. Delmas Lascorz, P. Judd, D. M. Stuart, Z. Poulos, M. Mahmoud, S. Sharify, M. Nikolic, K. Siu, and A. Moshovos, "Bit-tactical: A software/hardware approach to exploiting value and bit sparsity in neural networks," in *Proceedings of the 24th International Conference on Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems (ASPLOS)*, 2019, pp. 749–763.
- [12] P. H. E. Becker, J.-M. Arnau, and A. González, "Kd bonsai: Isa-extensions to compress kd trees for autonomous driving tasks," in *Proceedings of the 50th Annual International Symposium on Computer Architecture (ISCA)*, 2023, pp. 1–13.
- [13] J. Elseberg, D. Borrmann, and A. Nüchter, "One billion points in the cloud—an octree for efficient processing of 3d laser scans," *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, vol. 76, pp. 76–88, 2013.
- [14] X. Feng, C. Tang, Z. Zhang, W. Sun, and Y. Liu, "Semantic guided fine-grained point cloud quantization framework for 3d object detection," in *Proceedings of the 28th Asia and South Pacific Design Automation Conference (ASP-DAC)*, 2023, pp. 390–395.
- [15] Y. Feng, G. Hammonds, Y. Gan, and Y. Zhu, "Crescent: taming memory irregularities for accelerating deep point cloud analytics," in *Proceedings of the 49th Annual International Symposium on Computer Architecture (ISCA)*, 2022, pp. 962–977.
- [16] Y. Feng, B. Tian, T. Xu, P. Whatmough, and Y. Zhu, "Mesorasi: Architecture support for point cloud analytics via delayed-aggregation," in *Proceedings of the 53rd Annual IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Microarchitecture (MICRO)*, 2020, pp. 1037–1050.
- [17] A. Geiger, P. Lenz, and R. Urtasun, "Are we ready for autonomous driving? the kitti vision benchmark suite," in *Proceedings of Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2012.

- [18] A. Gholami, S. Kim, Z. Dong, Z. Yao, M. W. Mahoney, and K. Keutzer, "A survey of quantization methods for efficient neural network inference," in *Low-Power Computer Vision*, 2022, pp. 291–326.
- [19] M. R. Guthaus, J. E. Stine, S. Ataei, B. Chen, B. Wu, and M. Sarwar, "Openram: An open-source memory compiler," in *Proceedings of the IEEE/ACM International Conference on Computer-Aided Design (ICCAD)*, 2016, pp. 1–6.
- [20] N. Hajinazar, G. F. Oliveira, S. Gregorio, J. D. Ferreira, N. M. Ghiasi, M. Patel, M. Alser, S. Ghose, J. Gómez-Luna, and O. Mutlu, "SimDRAM: a framework for bit-serial simd processing using dram," in *Proceedings of the 26th ACM International Conference on Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems (ASPLOS)*, 2021, pp. 329–345.
- [21] M. Han, L. Wang, L. Xiao, H. Zhang, C. Zhang, X. Xu, and J. Zhu, "Quickfpts: Architecture and algorithm co-design for farthest point sampling in large-scale point clouds," *IEEE Transactions on Computer-Aided Design of Integrated Circuits and Systems*, 2023.
- [22] Inc. Micron Technology, "8Gb: x4, x8, x16 DDR4 SDRAM," <https://www.micron.com/products/dram/ddr4-sdram/part-catalog/mt40a512m16ly-062e>, 2021.
- [23] P. Judd, J. Albericio, T. Hetherington, T. M. Aamodt, and A. Moshovos, "Stripes: Bit-serial deep neural network computing," in *Proceedings of the 49th Annual IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Microarchitecture (MICRO)*, 2016, pp. 1–12.
- [24] H. Kaul, M. A. Anders, S. K. Mathew, G. Chen, S. K. Satpathy, S. K. Hsu, A. Agarwal, and R. K. Krishnamurthy, "14.4 a 21.5 m-query-vectors/s 3.37 nj/vector reconfigurable k-nearest-neighbor accelerator with adaptive precision in 14nm tri-gate cmos," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference (ISSCC)*, 2016, pp. 260–261.
- [25] S. Li, Z. Yang, D. Reddy, A. Srivastava, and B. Jacob, "Dramsim3: A cycle-accurate, thermal-capable dram simulator," *IEEE Computer Architecture Letters*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 106–109, 2020.
- [26] S. Li and N. Amenta, "Brute-force k-nearest neighbors search on the gpu," in *Proceedings of the 8th Similarity Search and Applications (SISAP)*, 2015, pp. 259–270.
- [27] Y. Lin, Z. Zhang, H. Tang, H. Wang, and S. Han, "Pointacc: Efficient point cloud accelerator," in *Proceedings of the 54th Annual IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Microarchitecture (MICRO)*, 2021, pp. 449–461.
- [28] K. Liu, A. Lu, K. Samtani, Z. Fang, and L. Guo, "Chip-knnv2: A configurable and high-performance k-nearest neighbors accelerator on hbm-based fpgas," *ACM Transactions on Reconfigurable Technology and Systems*, 2023.
- [29] LSLIDAR, "Lslidar ms03 user manual v1.0.1," <https://www.manualslib.com/manual/2843960/Lslidar-Ms03.html>, 2023.
- [30] H. Men, B. Gebre, and K. Pochiraju, "Color point cloud registration with 4d icp algorithm," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2011, pp. 1511–1516.
- [31] C. Mu, Y. Wang, J. Zheng, S. Liu, K. Zhou, S. Tang, C. Chen, and Q. Liu, "A 200m-query-vector/s computing-in-rram adc-less k-nearest-neighbor accelerator with time-domain winner-takes-all circuits," in *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Circuits and Systems (AICAS)*, 2022, pp. 222–225.
- [32] M. Muja and D. G. Lowe, "Fast approximate nearest neighbors with automatic algorithm configuration." *VISAPP (1)*, vol. 2, no. 331-340, p. 2, 2009.
- [33] R. Mur-Artal, J. M. M. Montiel, and J. D. Tardos, "Orb-slam: a versatile and accurate monocular slam system," *IEEE transactions on robotics*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 1147–1163, 2015.
- [34] F. B. Muslim, A. Demian, L. Ma, L. Lavagno, A. Qamar *et al.*, "Energy-efficient fpga implementation of the k-nearest neighbors algorithm using opencl," in *FedCSIS (Position Papers)*, 2016, pp. 141–145.
- [35] X. Peng, Y. Wang, and M.-C. Yang, "Chopper: A compiler infrastructure for programmable bit-serial simd processing using memory in dram," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on High-Performance Computer Architecture (HPCA)*, 2023, pp. 1275–1288.
- [36] R. Pinkham, S. Zeng, and Z. Zhang, "Quickknn: Memory and performance optimization of kd tree based nearest neighbor search for 3d point clouds," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International symposium on high performance computer architecture (HPCA)*, 2020, pp. 180–192.
- [37] robosense, "robosense ruby plus series product presentation," <https://www.robosense.cn/en/resources-89>, 2024.
- [38] D. Rozenberszki and A. L. Majdik, "Lol: Lidar-only odometry and localization in 3d point cloud maps," in *Proceedings of IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2020, pp. 4379–4385.
- [39] S. Ryu, H. Kim, W. Yi, and J.-J. Kim, "Bitblade: Area and energy-efficient precision-scalable neural network accelerator with bitwise summation," in *Proceedings of the 56th Annual Design Automation Conference (DAC)*, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [40] J. Saikia, S. Yin, Z. Jiang, M. Seok, and J.-s. Seo, "K-nearest neighbor hardware accelerator using in-memory computing sram," in *Proceedings of the IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Low Power Electronics and Design (ISLPED)*, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [41] V. Seshadri, D. Lee, T. Mullins, H. Hassan, A. Boroumand, J. Kim, M. A. Kozuch, O. Mutlu, P. B. Gibbons, and T. C. Mowry, "Ambit: In-memory accelerator for bulk bitwise operations using commodity dram technology," in *Proceedings of the 50th Annual IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Microarchitecture (MICRO)*, 2017, pp. 273–287.
- [42] S. Sharify, A. D. Lascorz, K. Siu, P. Judd, and A. Moshovos, "Loom: Exploiting weight and activation precisions to accelerate convolutional neural networks," in *Proceedings of the 55th Annual Design Automation Conference (DAC)*, 2018, pp. 1–6.
- [43] H. Sun, X. Liu, Q. Deng, W. Jiang, S. Luo, and Y. Ha, "Efficient fpga implementation of k-nearest-neighbor search algorithm for 3d lidar localization and mapping in smart vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs*, vol. 67, no. 9, pp. 1644–1648, 2020.
- [44] P. Sun, H. Kretzschmar, X. Dotiwalla, A. Chouard, V. Patnaik, P. Tsui, J. Guo, Y. Zhou, Y. Chai, B. Caine *et al.*, "Scalability in perception for autonomous driving: Waymo open dataset," in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (CVPR)*, 2020, pp. 2446–2454.
- [45] J. Vieira, R. P. Duarte, and H. C. Neto, "knn-stuff: knn streaming unit for fpgas," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 170 864–170 877, 2019.
- [46] Y. Wang, Y. Sun, Z. Liu, S. E. Sarma, M. M. Bronstein, and J. M. Solomon, "Dynamic graph cnn for learning on point clouds," *ACM Transactions on Graphics (tog)*, vol. 38, no. 5, pp. 1–12, 2019.
- [47] X. Xin, Y. Zhang, and J. Yang, "Elp2im: Efficient and low power bitwise operation processing in dram," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on High Performance Computer Architecture (HPCA)*, 2020, pp. 303–314.
- [48] T. Xu, B. Tian, and Y. Zhu, "Tigris: Architecture and algorithms for 3d perception in point clouds," in *Proceedings of the 52nd Annual IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Microarchitecture (MICRO)*, 2019, pp. 629–642.
- [49] J. Yang, Z. Zhang, Z. Liu, J. Zhou, L. Liu, S. Wei, and S. Yin, "Fusekna: Fused kernel convolution based accelerator for deep neural networks," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on High-Performance Computer Architecture (HPCA)*, 2021, pp. 894–907.
- [50] X. Yang, T. Fu, G. Dai, S. Zeng, K. Zhong, K. Hong, and Y. Wang, "An efficient accelerator for point-based and voxel-based point cloud neural networks," in *Proceedings of the 60th ACM/IEEE Design Automation Conference (DAC)*, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [51] J. Zhang and S. Singh, "Low-drift and real-time lidar odometry and mapping," *Autonomous Robots*, vol. 41, pp. 401–416, 2017.
- [52] J.-F. Zhang and Z. Zhang, "Pointx: A spatial-locality-aware architecture for energy-efficient graph-based point-cloud deep learning," in *Proceedings of the 54th Annual IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Microarchitecture (MICRO)*, 2021, pp. 1078–1090.
- [53] Z. Zhang, "Iterative closest point (icp)," in *Computer vision: a reference guide*. Springer, 2021, pp. 718–720.
- [54] J. Zheng, H. Jiang, X. Nie, Z. Huang, C. Chen, and Q. Liu, "Tipu: A spatial-locality-aware near-memory tile processing unit for 3d point cloud neural network," in *Proceedings of the 60th ACM/IEEE Design Automation Conference (DAC)*, 2023, pp. 1–6.